

Upscaling of Carbon-Based Perovskite Solar Module

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Abstract

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) and modules are driving the energy revolution in the coming photovoltaic field. In the last 10 years, PSCs reached efficiency close to the silicon photovoltaic technology by adopting low-cost solution processes. Despite this, the noble metal (such as gold and silver) used in PSCs as a counter electrode made these devices costly in terms of energy, CO₂ footprint, and materials. Carbon-based perovskite solar cells (C-PSCs) and modules use graphite/carbon-black-based material as the counter electrode. The formulation of low-cost carbon-based inks and pastes makes them suitable for large area coating techniques and hence a solid technology for imminent industrialization. Here, we want to present the upscaling routes of carbon-counter-electrode-based module devices in terms of materials formulation, architectures, and manufacturing processes in order to give a clear vision of the scaling route and encourage the research in this green and sustainable direction.

Keywords

perovskite solar cells; upscaling; carbon counter electrode; module

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19 **1. Introduction**

20 In the last decade, Perovskite earns a lot of attraction in solar technology as photoactive material due to the high
21 carrier mobility, ambipolar transport properties and bandgap tunability [1–3]. Since its discovery in 2009 [3], the
22 perovskite solar cell (PSC) technology reached a power conversion efficiency of 25.7% for the single junction and
23 31.25% in tandem with silicon [4,5]. The excellent optoelectronic and light-absorbing properties joint to the facile and
24 low-cost fabrication are leading this technology to be industrialized and able to supplant the well-established silicon
25 photovoltaics [1].

26 PSCs are made on top of a glass/plastic substrate coated with a Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) that work
27 as a front electrode. The absorber is sandwiched between a p-type (HTM, Hole Transporting Material) and n-type
28 (or ETM, Electron Transporting Material) semiconductors to improve the charge extraction from perovskite. A top
29 metal electrode (Au, Ag, Cu) completes the device. Perovskite devices could adopt direct (n-i-p) or inverted (p-i-n)
30 configuration (figure 1a and 1b). n-i-p or p-i-n junctions are equally used, and which is the most efficient and stable
31 configuration is still under debate in the scientific community [6–8].

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42 Figure 1. a) Direct/n-i-p and b) inverted/p-i-n perovskite solar cell

44 The n-i-p configuration could be divided into two classes that differ in the ETM materials and the relative struc-
45 ture. The mesoscopic structure employs two layers (compact and mesoporous) of titanium oxide and was used for
46 the first time in DSSC (Dye-sensitized Solar Cell) technology, then transferred to solid-state perovskite devices
47 [4,9,10]. The compact TiO₂ (c-TiO₂), works as electron blocking layer (EBL) and avoids recombination pathways of
48 photogenerated electrons from perovskite, while the mesoporous TiO₂ grants the electron transport to the BL and

49 increases the surface contact with perovskite. The planar n-i-p configuration is made by a thin film of different metal
50 oxide (e.g. Tin Oxide) deposit directly on top of the TCO [11–14]. The state of art HTM molecule is the 2,2',7,7'-
51 tetrakis (*N,N*-di-methoxy-phenylamine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene (spiro-OMeTAD) that provides high efficiencies. Poly-
52 triarylamine derivatives (e.g. PTAA) and others highly conjugated organic core are also used [7,15–17]. Gold metal
53 electrode is evaporated on top of device for his excellent conductivity and bandgap alignment.

54 The inverted structure (p-i-n) have opposite configuration, starting with the HTM material on the front elec-
55 trode, perovskite, ETL, and back metal electrode. Inorganic HTLs such as NiO_x, CuI or CuSCN claim higher chemical
56 stability than the organic ones and are suitable choices for HTM material in this type of structure [18–20]. On top of
57 perovskite generally the ETL is made by combining C60 and BCP (bathocuproine)[18–21]. In the end copper or silver
58 electrodes are evaporated on top of ETL to finalize the device.

59 Perovskite properties and stability is still under debate [22–24]. It is well-known that perovskite grants low
60 fabrication costs because can be easily processed through precursors solution respect Si or CIGS technologies [25,26].
61 Despite this, device stability is still an open issue because of the sensibility of the photoactive material to humidity
62 and micro-structure defects [6,23,24,27]. Moreover, the low stability of the large part of organic molecule used as
63 HTM and their dopants [28–30], and the diffusion of metal atoms from the electrode into perovskite is still an open
64 issue [31]. Different strategies are adopted to sort the problems related to perovskite [32–37] and HTM instability,
65 [38,39] but few works focused on issues related to the metal counter-electrode problem. As mentioned before, the
66 most used counter-electrode for perovskite devices is made of a high-cost metal like gold or silver. In this case, the
67 deposition process requires ultra-vacuum condition ($10^{-6}/10^{-7}$ bar) increasing the costs and makes arduous the pro-
68 cess scalability. Moreover, stability of the device will be compromise due to the ions migration of metal atoms from
69 the back contact into the transport and active layers. These are the major reasons why metal electrodes have a huge
70 CO₂ footprint and cannot be considered the first choice for a sustainable perovskite industrialization [40]. Despite
71 this, metal electrodes grant better efficiencies respect to other types of counter-electrodes.

72 Carbon-based perovskite technology is a concept born to improve the stability of PSCs and to lowering the cost
73 of the manufacturing process of PSCs. This material was used in DSSCs as electrode for the first time and later
74 applied also in solid state photovoltaics [41–46]. Carbon-based electrodes are widely applied in PSCs because of their
75 chemical inertness, hydrophobic nature, thermal stability and compatibility with up-scalable deposition techniques
76 (e.g. screen-printing, blade-coating), signifying their solid potential for mass-production [47–54]. Moreover, the ap-
77 proximate work function of 5.0 eV makes carbon a convenient counter-electrode material for perovskite solar cells
78 [55,56]. Here we want to present a short overview about carbon-based devices and their manufacturing processes
79 looking on the different upscaling strategies that are the core of this emerging technology.
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81 2. Materials and Methods

82 2.1. Carbon Electrodes

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84 In PSCs, carbon-based electrode demonstrated the ability to extract photogenerated holes from perovskite by them-
85 selves, opening the opportunity for researcher to explore HTLs free monolithic perovskite solar cell [57–59]. The
86 control of graphite and carbon amounts inside precursor paste provide the optimal electrical properties according
87 to the final device. Depending on which binder is used to realize the paste, carbon electrode could be obtained by
88 high-temperature (500 °C) or low-temperature curing (generally ≤ 120 °C).[60,61]
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90 2.1.1. High Temperature Carbon Electrodes (HTCEs)

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92 High-temperature carbon electrodes (HTCEs) are the first ones used in perovskite photovoltaics [62]. The core of the
93 cell architecture is based on a fully mesoscopic structure made of three highly porous layers called triple-mesoscopic
94 configuration. After the deposition of the anatase mp-TiO₂ layer, a porous ZrO₂ or Al₂O₃ spacer insulator layer avoids
95 recombination and shunts with respect to the porous carbon counter-electrode. All porous layers need high-temper-
96 ature curing, about 400-500 °C. Perovskite is added by percolation through the carbon electrode by different coating
97 techniques [62–65]. The easy fabrication of fully-printable triple-mesoscopic carbon-based (TiO₂/ZrO₂ or Al₂O₃/Car-
98 bon) perovskite solar cell has gained wide attention due to the exceptional stability and strong upscaling potential

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of such devices [62,63,66]. First application of the triple mesoscopic device is reported in 2013 with a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 6.6% [56]. Nowadays substantial improvements in performance are made till a PCE above 17% [67,68]. Although their good qualities, triple-mesoscopic-carbon perovskite solar cells show different issues such as the complete removal of solvent from Perovskite percolated into the mesoscopic structure, the thickness of spacing layers, the poor filling of Perovskite through a very thick carbon film (20-40 μm) and the photo-absorber morphology [69–71]. Moreover, the absence of any selective contact for photogenerated holes causes recombination pathways at the interface with perovskite. In this context, Raptis et al. implemented metallic grids inside carbon layer for better conductivity (figure 2a) [72]. The stack utilized is TCO/ TiO_2 / ZrO_2 /Carbon where 25 μm of copper grids were applied between two layers of carbon. On the same stack configuration, Jiang et al. worked on precursor solution concentration demonstrating how a systematic study on Perovskite precursors solution led to an efficiency above 16% [67]. Liu et al. found critical parameters in the layers thickness that can improve the efficiencies and avoid poor filling issue of the full-printable stack (figure 2b) [70]. Liu et al. added a selective mesoporous layer of NiO_x as HTL in FTO/ TiO_2 / Al_2O_3 / NiO_x /Carbon device configuration. NiO_x accelerate the extraction of photogenerated holes and improve photovoltaic performance up to 17,02% [68]. In literature, there are many approaches to solve the efficiency gap with respect to gold-based devices. The main strategies are focused on the charge extraction through hole Fermi level shift, the increase of carbon electrode conductivity, optimization of precursor solutions and thickness of all the involved layers [67,68,70,72–74]. Despite these improvements, the high environmental and cost impact related to the high temperature processes and non-radiative losses induced by the stack morphology reduces the feasibility in an industrial scale [40,75]. In addition, there are limited materials (e.g. inorganic HTM) compatible with high temperature curing [39].

Figure 2. a) Stack configuration with Cu metal grids b) SEM top view and cross section of FTO/ TiO_2 / ZrO_2 /PVK/Carbon and illustration about perovskite poor filling issue . Figure 2a and 2b are reprint with permissions from reference [72] and [70] respectively.

2.1.2. Low-Temperature Carbon Electrodes (LTCEs)

In the recent years, low-temperature carbon electrodes (LTCEs) in PSCs earned a lot of attention for their low-cost manufacturing and long-term stability [76,77]. Moreover, improving binder formulation to realize the carbon paste or ink make possible to get a good film with low temperature annealing processes. LTCEs are used both in n-i-p (mesoscopic or planar) and p-i-n configuration [50,56,78–81]. LTCEs grant selective holes transport, a good conductivity for external contact, thermal and chemical stability and high hydrophobicity [78]. This type of counter-electrode and its relative low curing temperature permit a deposition directly on top of the perovskite, without poor filling and morphology control issue respect HTCEs. Furthermore, organic/inorganic HTM can be used to achieve better charge extraction and efficiencies. The first attempt to make a device with LTCEs was made by Wei et al. by printing directly the carbon ink with Perovskite without any HTM as interlayer with an efficiency above 11% [82]. With the growth of interest for these materials, many techniques and optimizations were implemented in C-PSCs including HTMs between PVSK and carbon electrode and phase engineering of active material. Recently, the incorporation of graphene-doped P3HT as HTM in C-PSCs show excellent PCEs above 18% (figure 3a and 3b) with a shelf-life and light soaking stability of 1600 and 600 hours, respectively [76]. Formamidinium-based perovskite coupled with Spiro-OMeTAD and pressed LTCE foils demonstrate the biggest efficiency for these devices above 20% with 1000 h of shelf-life stability [83]. Metal phthalocyanine [84,85], CuSCN [86], P3HT/ NiO_x -CNT[76,87], NiO nanoparticles [88], $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ [89], TPDI [90] are new relevant examples of HTMs employed with low temperature

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carbon electrode. Lately, low-dimension perovskite layer employing large cations like Phenethyl Ammonium Iodide (PEAI) and Octyl Ammonium Iodide (OAI) were used on top of 3D Perovskite with LTCEs for interfacial engineering and 2D perovskite growth with promising efficiencies of 15.6 and 18.5 % (figure 3c and 3d), respectively [91,92]. Calabrò et al. show the thermal (85 °C) stability improvement of KI-doped perovskite cell by substituting the gold counter-electrode with a LTCE [93]. He et al. doped the carbon paste with a small amount of CuPC as p-dopant to modify the work function of the electrode and improve the band gap alignment. The PCE enhanced by 10% with respect to the bare carbon (from 12.8% to 14.8% for record cell) and the stability of encapsulated devices reached 1000 h under continuous one sun illumination at 45°C [94]. In the recent years, LTCEs are also coupled with flexible substrates in perovskite solar technology as shown by Babu et al. incorporating a thin layer of chromium between PCBM and carbon getting an efficiency above 15% and remarkable stability over 1000 h in shelf-life and at 85°C in nitrogen environment [77].

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Figure 3. a) Stack configuration, b) best JV curve (reverse and forward), shelf-life and light-soaking stability for PSCs with P3HT/Graphene as HTM using LTCE c) Stack, d) statistics on photovoltaic parameters, and light soaking test in nitrogen without encapsulation for 3D perovskite and 3D/2D perovskite carbon-based devices. All images are reprinted with permission from references [76] (figure 3a and 3b) and reference [92] (figure 3c and 3d)

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2.2. Methodologies

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The upscaling of perovskite photovoltaic technology from small area cells to modules, and the related industrial and economical transition, is achievable by scalable manufacturing processes, module design and interconnection patterning [26,95,96]. The first point is related to the deposition of the full stack by scalable deposition techniques. In literature, many efforts are related to the deposition of the perovskite layer to get homogeneous and highly efficient modules [97]. The carbon-based devices give the chance to deposit the full stack by printing techniques. Here, we just mention the most popular scalable deposition technique to obtain HT and LT carbon electrodes (figure 4a, 4b, 4c and 4d). Blade-coating/doctor-blading technique deposits material using a blade on rigid or flexible substrate. High homogeneous films are obtained by modifying the material amount, the meniscus gap, the concentration and the composition of precursors solutions. After deposition, annealing process is required, sometimes in a vacuum chamber to make more efficient the solvents/binders evaporation [98]. Screen-printing technique adopts a patterned screen to deposit controlled thickness material amount. These scalable deposition methods could be implemented in manufacturing processes such as roll-to-roll [70,84,90,99]. Press transfer and hot press are alternative methods to obtain single carbon film on to the substrate [100–102]. This type of techniques

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avoids annealing process and preserves organic HTM or passivating agent on top of Perovskite. In this case, the carbon film is obtained by printing techniques, then with solvent exchange or mechanical peeling-off the film is picked up from the substrate and mechanically implemented through a press onto the solar device.

Figure 4. a) Blade coating deposition of carbon material and vacuum/heat treatment for fast drying the film b) solvent exchange used to obtain carbon film c) Schematic structure of carbon paste printing with screen-printing technique d) mechanical peeling-off of carbon film and incorporation into the solar device. Figures 4a and 4b are reproduced from references [98] and [100] respectively. Figures 4c and 4d are reproduced from references [102] and [103] respectively.

Though spin-coating, ink-jet printing and spray-coating techniques are less used to obtain carbon counter-electrodes, because of the adopted viscous binders (e.g. ethylene glycol), in literature different examples are present exhibiting competitive efficiencies [104–106].

3. Upscaling Carbon-Based Perovskite Technology

One of the main goal achievable with carbon-based perovskite technology is the possibility to have an upscaled process for the full stack. Carbon material combines good electrical properties with easy manufacturing processes

258 thanks to the optimization of carbon-paste formulations and related deposition methods. These features together
259 with the high stability make carbon a real candidate to supplant costly metal electrodes in perovskite technology.
260 Here, we report the main results obtained on module devices working with HTCE and LTCE.
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262 3.1. High temperature carbon electrodes perovskite devices upscaling

263 In 2013, Ku et al. showed the first HTCE heterojunction perovskite solar cell by printable deposition method with
264 an efficiency of 6.64% [62]. Over the last 9 years, many large area Perovskite modules working with carbon counter-
265 electrode were reported in literature. In 2016, Priyadarshi et al. reported a monolithic perovskite module with active
266 area of 70 cm², PCE of 10.74% and ambient stability of more than 2000 h. The meso-TiO₂/ZrO₂/carbon stack was
267 deposited by screen-printing technique and the perovskite absorber was obtained by drop-casting method [107].
268 Grancini et al. demonstrated the stability of 5-AVAI/MAPI perovskite solar module with 2D/3D Perovskite interface
269 engineering [108]. The fabrication of 10x10 cm² solar modules by a fully printable industrial-scale process reached
270 11.2% efficiency with zero loss at 1 sun AM 1.5 G, 55°C for 10000 h (figure 5a) [108]. 5-AVAI is also used by Hu et al.
271 combined with γ -butirrolactone (GBL) to control Perovskite solvent evaporation after infiltration step. The authors
272 presented 7 m² solar panel fully fabricated with printable techniques (figure 5b) [63]. De Rossi et al. use 5-
273 AVAI/MAPI Perovskite in triple mesoscopic module with 198 cm² active area and an efficiency of 6.6% after storing
274 module in dark at 50-70% RH [109]. Thus, they show how the patterning optimization of blocking layer could
275 improve device performances. More recently, a modified mesoporous scaffold with CsX (X= Halide, figure 5c) salts
276 showed a boosted open circuit voltage of 960 mV with respect to the reference 920 mV on cells (0.7 cm² active area)
277 and modules (70 cm²) with a PCE of 12.59% and 11.55%, respectively and stability over 2000 h in ambient condition
278 [110]. Xu et al. present 60.08 cm² active area module with a controlled infiltration method by slot-die coating. The
279 control of precursor solution and deposition of perovskite above triple-mesoscopic scaffold grant a final PCE of
280 12.87% which is the highest value reported for such big devices (60 cm²) [111]. Lately, Kobayashi et al. reported an
281 evaluation about the stability of HTC-based devices. They show 4.32 cm² active area modules with triple mesoscopic
282 high temperature stack (meso-TiO₂/ZrO₂/carbon) [112]. The module had PCE equal to 8.7% and was stable in damp-
283 heat aging condition (85°C/85% RH) stability tests for more than 3000 hours. This stability is attributed to the light-
284 induced performance increasing phenomenon. The mechanism is associated to the organic molecules 5-
285 ammoniumvaleric acid and methylammonium forming a quasi-2-dimensional perovskite/metal oxide interface
286 with a positive effect on charge transport and suppression of ion migration [112].

287 3.2. Low temperature carbon electrodes perovskite devices upscaling

288 In literature, few works are present regarding the LTCE-based module fabrication. In 2017, Cai et al. coupled gas-
289 pumping perovskite with slot die-coating method and low temperature carbon electrode [113]. This approach lead
290 to reproducible solar modules (FTO/ZnO/PVK/Carbon) with 17.6 cm² active area, PCE of 10.6% and no significant
291 degradation after 140 days of outdoor testing [114]. In 2019, He et al. reported a full-low temperature processed n-i-
292 p mesoscopic module by doping the carbon counter-electrode with copper (II) phtalocyanine. The aperture area was
293 22.4 cm², the geometrical fill factor 89.6% and the efficiency 7.2% [94]. In 2021, Yang et al. added 10% guanidinium
294 chloride (CH₆N₃⁺Cl⁻) to the perovskite precursor solution and used P3HT as HTM (figure 5e and 5f) [83]. The
295 morphology and crystallinity of perovskite film were greatly enhanced, resulting in enlarged grain sizes and lowered
296 defect densities. Moreover, they study the passivation of active layer with PDCBT and the interface engineering
297 between HTM and carbon with Ta-WO_x. All these optimizations lead to amazing efficiency of 15.3% on 4 cm² module
298 with a full-printable fabrication process.

Figure 5. a) JV curve of 2D/3D perovskite with 3% AVAI in 10x10cm² module and module stability test under 1 sun b) 7 m² printable perovskite solar panels with HTCE and illustration of ideal product line c) JV curves with and without CsBr modified TiO₂ solar HTCE module and shelf-life stability (inset)d) Picture and JV curve of HTCE solar module with slot-die coating perovskite infiltration e) module stack, f) JV curve and picture of low temperature carbon module on 25 cm² substrate using P3HT as HTM. Figures 5a and 5b are reproduced with the permission from references[108] and [63] respectively; figures 5c and 5d are reproduced from references [110] and [111] respectively. Figures 5e and 5f are reproduced with permission from reference [83].

	Deposition Method of carbon layer	Module active area	Voc [V]	Isc [mA]	FF [%]	PCE [%] (fwd)	Stability Tests	Stack Configuration	Ref
High-Temperature carbon modules	Screen-printing	49 cm ² (10 cells)	9.3	98	56	10.4 (10.4)	1) 1000 h light soaking at 1 sun 2) 30 days outdoor test 3) 1 year shelf-life in dark	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[63]
	Screen-printing	70 cm ² (10 cells)	9.63	124	63	10.74 (10.10)	2000 h shelf life	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[107]
	Screen-printing	47.6 cm ² (7 cells)	7.05	104.7	70	11.16 (-)	12.000 h at 1 sun AM 1.5 G conditions at 55°C	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x (MA)1-xPbI ₃	[108]
	Screen-printing	198 cm ² (22 cells)	19.7	192	34	6.6 (5.7)	-	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[109]
	Screen-printing	70 cm ² (10 cells)	9.12	158.3	56	11.55 (11.24)	2700 h shelf life stability on small area cells at 60 % RH	FTO/cTiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[110]
	Screen-printing	60.08 cm ² (9 cells)	8.50	150.1	61	12.87 (-)	-	FTO/cTiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[111]
	Screen-printing	4.32 cm ² (3 cells)	2.4	10.8	34	8.7 (8.7)	3000 damp-heat 85°C/85 RH	FTO/cTiO ₂ /mTiO ₂ /mZrO ₂ /mCarbon/ (5-AVAI) _x MA1-xPbI ₃	[112]
Low-Temperature carbon modules	Doctor-blade	22.4 cm ²	6.4	53	47.5	7.2 (-)	-	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /MAPI/Carbon doped with CuPC	[94]
	Screen printing	17.6 cm ² (8 cells)	6.14	57.2	53	10.6 (-)	-	FTO/ZnO/MAPI/Carbon	[114]
	Blade coating	4 cm ² (Electrical values referred to sub-cell)	1.05	21.2	69	15.3 (-)	800 h at 85°C in nitrogen (on small area cells) 180 s MPP tracking on module	ITO/SnO ₂ /GAxMA1-xPbI ₃ /PDCBT/P3HT/Ta-WO _x /Carbon	[83]

343 Tab. 1 Reported deposition technique of carbon electrode, photovoltaic parameters, stability tests and device stack con-
344 figuration on perovskite solar module with high and low temperature carbon electrode.

346 Conclusions and Perspectives

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348 In few years, state-of-art perovskite solar cells and modules reached impressive efficiency. Metal electrodes are
349 intensively used even the high costs of material and process. The future of photovoltaic energy cannot base its growth
350 on high-cost material with high CO₂ footprint and energy consumption. Carbon-based materials are processable with
351 scalable techniques at high and low temperature as PSCs counter electrodes. In literature, we found different approach
352 to improve and scale-up HTCE on PSM technology both on modules and panels. Fully printable triple mesoscopic
353 devices are suitable choice for their facile adaptability in a possible pilot line production but, despite the excellent sta-
354 bility, huge differences in efficiency are still present for such devices with respect to the metal-based perovskite cells.
355 LTCE grants low temperature processing with relative less energy costs. Moreover, it is possible to use various HTM as
356 selective contact between perovskite and carbon material retaining perovskite morphology as well. All these features
357 will drive the fabrication of low temperature carbon based solar module with high efficiency and stability in the next
358 years. Nowadays, there is a lack in literature about LTCE-based modules. Many efforts should be oriented on scalable
359 processes for such devices starting from the laser interconnection patterning, that was not deeply detailed or explored.
360 Low temperature carbon-based PSCs have the chance to be the perovskite solar technology ready and suitable for the
361 market. The Efficiency is above 20% and the research community is moving the attention in this field respect to the
362 expensive and pollutant metal electrode-based PSCs. Here, we have reported the stat-of-art on HT and LT carbon-based
363 perovskite module to help researchers understanding the most feasible way to an efficient, stable and sustainable solar
364 device.

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366 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization, L.V.; methodology, M.S. and L.V.; validation, L.V.; investigation, M.S.; re-
367 sources, A.D.C.; writing—original draft preparation, M.S.; writing—review and editing, L.V.; visualization, M.S. and
368 L.V.; supervision, L.V. and A.D.C.; project administration, L.V. and A.D.C.; funding acquisition, A.D.C. and L.V.. All
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